

A Multi-Scale and Adaptive Track-Before-Detect Technique for Maritime Environments

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Abstract—Track-Before-Detect (TBD) is a detection technique that simultaneously tracks and detects a target. The technique is specially useful for targets whose back-scattered return is significantly lower than the surrounding noise and background environments. Different algorithms proposed to perform TBD include particle filter, dynamic programming and Hough transform algorithms have been proposed. These techniques work well in a highly noise environment with constant velocity targets. However, some of these techniques are not applicable to targets that have acceleration as well as targets embedded in sea clutter. In this paper, we present a beamlet track-before-detect technique for maritime detection. Due to the sea clutter, two different adaptive sea clutter filtering methods are applied before the aforementioned TBD technique. Overall, the paper introduces and studies a beamlet TBD technique for maneuverable maritime targets in sea clutter.

I. INTRODUCTION

In typical radar tracking, detections are formed by thresholding the output of the radar return and filtering the detection results. The detection threshold is usually chosen as a compromise between the false alarm rate and detection rate. If a target is to be tracked after detection, we may term this method as detect-before-track (DBT) technique. While this method works well for targets with high signal to interference (SNIR) values, targets with low signal-to-noise (SNR) and low signal-to-interference (SINR) may be masked if the signal power is below a required threshold. If the threshold is reduced, too many false alarm can overwhelm the tracking algorithm with false tracks. Track-before-detect (TBD) techniques [1] are a set of methods that simultaneously detect and track the target at the same time. This method works by evaluating possible trajectories over multiple scans of data, each one of which is treated like the one actually representing a target. At the decision moment, the candidate trajectories whose posterior probability are the highest are considered to be targets. After such a declaration, the trajectory of that detect target may be fed to a track-while-scan (TWS) algorithm. An accurate estimate of the target trajectory in the TBD stage can also provide a reliable initial values for the TWS.

Some of the different TBD algorithms that have been proposed are covered in [2] along with comparisons of performance in noise. These algorithms include dynamic programming, Bayesian approach, histogram probabilistic multi-hypothesis tracker, and particle filter TBD techniques [1][2]. Carlson et al. [3][4][5] use the Hough transform TBD for 2-

D data (range-time) to detect constant velocity targets embedded in noise. One major difference in approach between the method proposed by Carlson et al. and the methods in [1][2] should be noted. The former assumes that the target follows an unknown trajectory from a set of known candidate trajectories whereas the latter assumes that the target trajectory is an stochastic process. In the case of Hough transform, it is suitable for targets that have constant velocity. Moqiseh et al. demonstrated the utility of the Hough transform for three-dimensional range-bearing-time data cube at the cost of more computational requirements and memory storage [6]. Whereas the 2-D Hough space is a two parameter space, the 3-D hough space is a 5 parameter space.

In this work, we take the approach of assuming that the target follows an unknown trajectory that can be approximated by chaining together a set of multi-scale and multi-orientation line segments. We propose a more generalized algorithm relative to [3] by proposing the beamlet [7] TBD technique. The beamlet transform is a multi-scale evaluation of the X-ray transform and the X-ray transform is equivalent to the Hough transform for the case of discrete and binary data. By using the beamlet transform, we can consider the case of targets with acceleration, which are not handled well with the Hough transform method. For a target with acceleration, the Hough transform may confuse a single target for several targets. Our method contains the Hough transform technique as a special case. Although the results presented are for 2-D range-time space, one can also implement the beamlet transform in higher dimensional spaces [7]. Another contribution of this paper is that we provide simulation results of our method for the case of both noise and sea clutter [10], where-as all the TBD papers mentioned have only consider the noise case.

The organization of this paper is as follows. In Section II, we overview the general concept of TBD and how a transformed TBD like the Hough and beamlet transform are a special case of the maximum likelihood approach. Further insights are mentioned in this section with regards to the interconnection of match filtering and the aforementioned TBD techniques. In Section III, we give an overview of the beamlet transform. In Section IV, we review our sea clutter model along with two sea clutter suppression techniques. In section V, we present some simulation results with a generic search radar case. Discussions and possible future research directions are discussed in Section VI.

II. TRACK-BEFORE-DETECT

We denote the target state at a discrete time index k as $\mathbf{x}(k) = [(x(kT), \dot{x}(kT), \ddot{x}(kT))]$ where the evolution of the state is modelled by a linear deterministic process. We assume without a loss of generality that the discrete time index is a multiple of T , the scan per scan time interval. We also assume that for a coherent dwell, the target lies within the same azimuth-range sector and this is the case for a high PRF radar in maritime environments. Our deterministic model for motion is slightly different than the approach in [1][2] where the target is assumed to have a constant velocity with an added Gaussian noise process that models acceleration. Here we have directly taken acceleration into our state equation. From the time index m to $K + m - 1$, we may define a track as $\mathbf{X}[K] = [\mathbf{x}(m) \mathbf{x}(m+1) \dots \mathbf{x}(m+K-1)]$ where we have assumed K number of scans in the same azimuth sector. Consequently, we assume the dynamic trajectory of the targets evolves in a range-time plane. We can extend our TBD approach in this paper to higher dimensional hyper-cubes but the algorithm at its simplest case may be illustrated in 2-D range-time dataset without a loss of generality. The evolution of the state of the target $x(k)$ may be written as:

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}(k-1) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{F} is a 3x3 transition matrix which can be written as:

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & T & T^2/2 \\ 0 & 1 & T/2 \\ 0 & 1 & T \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

A set of measurement sequences where the target amplitude is embedded in noise and sea clutter may be denoted by $\mathbf{Z}[K] = [\mathbf{z}(m) \mathbf{z}(m+1) \dots \mathbf{z}(m+K-1)]$ where $\mathbf{z}(m)$ denotes the range-profile measurements at time mT . Each element of $\mathbf{z}(m)$ is denoted by $z_i(m)$ where the index i represents the i th range cell at the time index m . Given $\mathbf{Z}[K]$, we would like to detect the target and also its associated trajectory $\mathbf{X}[K]$. After K samples, the optimal solution for the detection of a target and its associated trajectory may be formulated as a greatest likelihood ratio test (LRT):

$$\arg \max_{\mathbf{X}[K]} \frac{P(\mathbf{Z}[K]|H1, \mathbf{X}[K])}{P(\mathbf{Z}[K]|H0)} \geq \gamma \quad (3)$$

Where $H0$ denotes the null hypothesis, $H1$ denotes the case where a target may be present and γ is a threshold set for the false alarm. However, due to the fact that the multi-dimensional probability distributions $P(\mathbf{Z}[K]|\mathbf{X}[K])$ is not analytically tractable for most practical cases of interest, we have to resort to a sub-optimal formulation. A frequently used method, which we shall use is to assume that the target is present for those candidate tracks whose associated non-coherently integrated amplitude exceed some threshold. This comparison test may be written as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}[K] = \left\{ \mathbf{X}[K] : \sum_{i=1}^K |z_i| (n) > \eta \right\} \quad (4)$$

where η is the threshold that which determines the probability of detection and probability of false alarm. The Hough transform used by Carlson et al. only encompasses the space of constant velocity tracks running from the boundary pixels of a two dimensional range-time dataset. This consists of only global scale line segments traversing the dataset completely from one boundary point to another. The beamlet transform allows for the analysis of fragments of line and also approximates curves accurately by using multi-scale and multi-orientation line segments. These line fragments or beamlets occur at multiple orientations and scales as described in the next section. We will use the beamlet transform to be able to detect both targets that are exposed in the middle of the R-T dataset as well as targets with non-constant velocity.

III. BEAMLET TBD

The 2-D X-ray transform on a continuous square is defined as the set of all line-integrals on the boundaries of datasets. The 2-D Hough transform is a special case of the X-ray for binary data and the 2-D X-ray transform is equivalent to the 2-D radon transform. The beamlet transform is in effect a multi-scale version of the X-ray transform and hence the X-ray transform is a special case of the beamlet transform. Here, we briefly overview the beamlet transform based on [7] and more details can be obtained therein. This is done in order that we may state an important properties for TBD application and also for the paper to be self-contained. In order to illustrate the beamlet concept, we consider a square (e.g. the range-time dataset) S as a continuum square $[0, 1]^2$. The data values on S are an array of $1/n$ by $1/n$ squares arranged on a grid of $[0, 1]^2$, where $n = 2^J$.

Definition 1: A dyadic square S for the scale j is the collection of points $\{(x_1, x_2) : [k_1/2^j, (k_1+1)/2^j]\}$ where $0 \leq k_1, k_2 < 2^j$ and $0 \leq j \leq J$.

We may write S as $S(k_1, k_2, j)$ so that for example $S(0, 0, 0)$ in the unit square $[0, 1]^2$ and $S(0, 0, 1)$ is the square $[0, 1/2]^2$. So for a n by n grid with $n = 2^J$, then the individual pixels are the n^2 cells $S(k_1, k_2, J)$ where $0 \leq k_1, k_2 < 2^J$.

Definition 2: A beam is a line segment b connecting any two vertices $\bar{v}_1 \bar{v}_2$ on $[0, 1]^2$.

Thus on $1/n$ by $1/n$ grid, if we consider only beams connecting vertices at pixels corners, there are $O(n^4)$ beams. We now take the collection of all dyadic squares at all scales $0 \leq j \leq J$, and fix a resolution $\alpha = 2^{-(J-L)}$ where $L \geq 0$. The boundary of each dyadic square is marked at the fix resolution α and there are precisely $M_j = 2^L 2^{J-j} 4$ vertices. On each dyadic square S with sides $2^{-j} \geq 1/n$, the collection of all beams connecting vertices may be written as $B_\alpha(S) = \{b = \bar{v}_{i_1, S} \bar{v}_{i_2, S} : 0 \leq i_1, i_2 < M_j\}$.

Definition 3: For a given dyadic α and n , the set of **beamlets** is the collection $\beta_{n, \alpha}$ of all beams belonging to

Fig. 1. Illustration of the basic concepts for the 2D beamlet dictionary courtesy of [12]. The left column shows dyadic squares at different scales while the right column illustrates beamlets at different scales

some $B_\alpha(S)$ for some dyadic square S of side-length 2^{-j} , $0 \leq j \leq J$.

We note that beamlets only connect vertices on the boundary of a dyadic square thus the collection of beamlets is much smaller than the collection of beams. The set of all beamlets is also called the beamlet dictionary. Figure 1 illustrates the set of 2-D dyadic squares is a hierarchially organized set which is obtained through partitioning of the original data square into smaller dyadic squares. The set of line segments connecting the vertices on each dyadic square are shown on the right and their totality constitutes the beamlet dictionary.

The beamlet transform of a continuous 2-D dataset $f(x_1, x_2)$ is the collection of the line integrals along all the beamlets $b \in \beta_{n,\alpha}$ and is given by:

$$T_f(b) = \int_b f(t(l))dl \quad (5)$$

where $t(l)$ traces out b along the unit path. The element of the set $T_f(\beta_{n,\alpha})$ are known as the beamlet coefficients. The computation cost of the beamlet transform is of the order $O((\frac{n}{\alpha})^2 \log_2(n))$ while the computational cost of calculating all line integrals along beams is of the order $O((\frac{n}{\alpha})^4)$ [7]. For a discrete dataset, the discrete beamlet transform is computed by using an interpolation functions[7]. In this work, we use the average interpolation function where the values of the discrete dataset are seen as a pixel level average of a continuous function. For the inverse beamlet transform, we use the method of [12] where an iterative inverse based on the Conjugate Gradient method for solving the least square problem is used. The beamlet transform satisfies the causality property [7] where data stored at the coarser scales should be derivable from data a higher scale.

Theorem 1: Any line with endpoints anywhere in $[0, 1]^2$ can

be approximated within Hausdorff distance $\alpha/2 + 1/n$ by a continuous chain (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m) of beamlets $b_i \in \beta_{n,\alpha}$ where the number m of beamlets required is bounded by $\log_2(n)$ for $n > 2$.

Proof: See [7] and references therein. Intuitively, this theorem allows us to approximate any curvilinear structure with arbitrary degree of accuracy that depends on n and α . If the scale is small relative to the curvature of the curve, any smooth curve would resemble a curvilinear structure. In this paper, the curvilinear structure is precisely the target trajectory in a discrete range-time dataset.

We now propose the beamlet TBD technique for radar detection. Our algorithm for the beamlet TBD follows the following psuedo-code:

Step 1: Compute the beamlet transform to obtain the beamlet coefficients at all scales.

Step 2: Keep the P highest coefficients for each epoch where an epoch is the length of the dyadic square of the coarsest scale.

Step 3: Apply the inverse beamlet transform.

Step 4: Chain the beamlets using good continuation with parameters θ and ρ .

Step 5: Output the longest chained beamlet path whose length is greater than a second threshold Λ as a potential target.

Step 4 which is the good continuation step follows the method of chaining beamlets in [9][12]. A beamlet chain is a collection of beamlets that makes up a possible trajectory. To explain step 4, we assume we have range-time dataset where time is on the horizontal axis. Also we assume that b_1 and b_2 are two beamlets where the tail of b_1 is less or equal to the head of b_2 . This corresponds to the fact that b_1 occurs in time before b_2 . If the acute angle between b_1 and b_2 is less than or equal to θ and the euclidean distance between the tail of b_1 and head of b_2 is less than ρ , then b_1 and b_2 follow the good continuation step with respect to each other. Thus we consider them to be part of the same chain (segment). Also, if the b_1 contains b_2 or vice versa, then we assume they are part of the same chain of beamlets.

In our TBD beamlet method, a false track detection occurs if an output beamlet chain with a length greater than Λ is obtained and there was no target present. A false track also occurs for a beamlet chain whose length is greater than or equal to Λ and whose maximum offset at any instance is d meters from the target trajectory. Similarly a missed detection occurs if there was a target present but the beamlet TBD was not able to detect it. Conversely, a correct detection is a beamlet chain greater than Λ and whose maximum estimated trajectory offset is within d meters of the actual target trajectory at all instances. To illustrate the accuracy of the beamlet TBD without interference, we have simulated an arbitrary motion (see Section 4 for parameters) of a point target in the R-T plane in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the output reconstruction of the curve after the Radon transform and the inverse Radon transform with the filtered back projection algorithm. Figure 4 shows the output reconstruction of the curve with the beamlet transform using scales of 4, 8, 16, 32, 64 and

Fig. 2. Illustration of the basic concepts for the 2D beamlet dictionary courtesy of [12]. The left column shows dyadic squares at different scales while the right column illustrates beamlets at different scales

Fig. 4. Reconstruction using beamlets

Fig. 3. Reconstruction using 2-D X-ray transform in dB scales

256. As shown, the beamlet and inverse beamlet transform reconstruct the curve without any loss in accuracy. However, the reconstruction with the radon transform has dispersed the energy of the curve throughout the whole observation area. For radar applications, these extraneous energies in the range-time cells that there target is not present can increase false alarm rates.

IV. SEA CLUTTER MODEL AND SUPPRESSION

We use the K distribution sea clutter model to generate synthetic clutter [10]. According to this interpretation, the K distribution envelope is a compound distribution consisting of a locally Rayleigh distribution speckle whose mean is modulated by a gamma distribution. Other compound distributions such as modulating the mean by the inverse gamma distribution [8] (also known as Pareto distribution) have also been proposed but the connection between the shape parameters to the physical radar parameters have not been tabulated. The parameters of the K-distribution in X-band based on empirical evidence is given by [10]:

$$\log_{10}(\nu) = \frac{2}{3}\log_{10}(\phi_{gr}) + \frac{5}{8}\log_{10}(A_c) - k_{pol} - \cos\left(\frac{2\theta_{sw}}{3}\right) \quad (6)$$

where ν is the shape parameter of the K distribution, ϕ_{gr} is the grazing angle, A_c is the radar resolved area, k_{pol} is the polarization dependent parameter and θ_{sw} is the aspect angle with respect to the swell direction which we assume to coincide with the wind direction. We used the memoryless non-linear transform (MLNT) and the Gauss-markov model to [10] induce range and time correlation in the clutter. The time correlation exponential decay parameter is varied in our simulation while the range-correlation decay parameter is taken from [11]. For sea clutter suppression we used two different approaches. The first approach is the cell-averaging constant false alarm filter [11] for filtering out the sea clutter. We use T_c adjacent cells on each side of the cell under test (CUT) and output the CUT with a soft detection rather than a binary-detection. For the second approach we adapt the soft cell-averaging CFAR method just described as follows: Let N_c be the number of pulses per scan for an azimuth sector. Then given the N_r range cells for each pulse, we train PCA components on $N_r - 1$ vectors wherein each vector consists of the N_p pulses for each azimuth sector. The last two PCA components are then used calculate the ratio of the coding error corresponding to the CUT and corresponding to the N_{r1} cells. Thereafter only N_{max} cells corresponding to maximal coding error ratios are retained (although this can be easily modified to allow only cell locations whose ratio error exceeds a pre-defined threshold). Due to the presence of greater correlation structure in the case of high-clutter the PCA approach just described is better able to perform clutter cancelation as compared to the cell-averaging CFAR. However in the case of pure i.i.d. noise, we find the latter to be more desirable in terms of visual quality of the clutter cancelled image. The need for soft output in the above algorithms is because we operate our beamlet TBD on the actual amplitude

values rather than binary values as in the Hough transform method. Using soft-detection, some gain is to be expected relative to hard-detection where only binary value is outputted. This is because for a small area, the cell with the target plus noise and clutter is expected to have an average higher amplitude than cells with only noise and clutter. In hard detection, these two would receive the same value of 1 if they cross the average threshold.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to assess the performance of our beamlet TBD, we assume a target model that under goes uniform acceleration as shown in Figure 2. More specifically, the target has a constant velocity for a period, then accelerates uniformly, then has a constant velocity and then undergoes a negative uniform acceleration for a period until it reaches a constant velocity where it is moving towards the radar. The target is captured on a 256 by 256 range-time grid. Table I shows the target acceleration at various times. Table II shows the Radar and simulation parameters. The distance from the radar to the target is one of the main factors that sets the shape parameter values of the clutter. For our simulation, $N_p = 16$ pulses have been non-coherently integrated in each scan and we assume that in the dwell time, the target is constant within a range cell. This assumption is valid for the PRF value we have used relative to the typical speed of maritime vehicles. Table IV shows the output of our simulation for the cell-averaging soft-detection clutter filter for various CNRs and SINR values. Table V shows the progressive improvement of the detection rate as a function of increasing SNIR for a CNR of 30 dB. Each result was computed through 100 monte-carlo simulation runs. The correlation time exponential decay parameter for the sea clutter is $T_s = 2$ while the exponential decay parameter for range-correlation is $T_r = 11.5$ meters. The parameters for the beamlet TBD were set according to Table III. We also eliminated all beamlets where the target moves more than 2 range cell per scan. For a faster moving target or smaller range resolution, this last restriction may be removed. Based on the range-correlation, the number of cells to average on each side of the CUT is $T_c = 10$. Figures 5 and 6 illustrate two simulation points for SINR values of 0 and 5 dB at a CNR value of 30 dB after step 3 of the beamlet TBD algorithm. Figure 7 shows a case of an SNIR of 0 dB and a CNR of 30 dB. Overall, the beamlet TBD does well in noise region. In the case of high clutter regions, it does well in the range of 4 to 10 dB. However, we get no detection at 0 dB in the high clutter region. For the case of -10 dB, the beamlet transform was not able to find the target at all. It may be possible to use more scans at a cost of more computational time or increase P at the cost of false alarms in order to detect the target at such an SNIR. When performing the above experiments for the PCA clutter suppression approach, preliminary results show for a higher bandwidth of 400 MHz, the PCA outperforms the cell-average approach at higher CNR values, but for a bandwidth of 150 MHz, the cell-average approach is slightly better. However, we will investigate this phenomenon further in future work.

TABLE I
TARGET MOTION

Time (sec)	0-8	8-16	16-32	32-48	48-64
Acceleration m/s^2	0	0.375	0	-0.1875	0

VI. CONCLUSION

We introduced and studied a specific beamlet TBD technique for maritime environments. We should however note that the authors in [7] are to be credited for introducing beamlets for finding curvilinear structures. Due to the fact that beamlets are multi-scale and multi-orientation line segments, they can approximate curved structures well. The beamlet TBD algorithm can perform multiple scan integration of targets with curved trajectories. We should also note that beamlet TBD algorithm is also parallelizable for the computation of the beamlet coefficients as well the beamlet chaining step we described. The algorithm contains as a special case, the Hough transform TBD. In our simulation runs, we noticed a severe performance degradation relative to noise in the clutter region for SNIRs below 5 dB. We did not attempt to optimize the parameters such as P and this could be a subject of future research. Increasing P beyond a certain threshold might output too many false alarms but also the target as well. This may be benign if further post-processing beyond the good-continuation algorithm is accomplished or the TWS tracking algorithm can handle these false track scenarios. However, more analytic and simulation results are needed to understand the effects of the various beamlet parameters on the detection and false track rates. For future work, we will need to study how changing P affects performance. Allowing P to increase may produce false tracks but improve detection. In terms of clutter suppression, we plan to further investigate the relative advantage of the PCA approach for higher bandwidths. Also multiple target scenarios as well as comparisons to other algorithms in terms of accuracy and speed needs further research. Furthermore, extension of the algorithm to 3-D (range-azimuth-time) is possible although the algorithm complexity will increase by a square factor to $O(n^4 \log_2(n^4))$.

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TABLE II
RADAR DESCRIPTORS

Operation Frequency	X-band (9.5-10.0 Ghz)
Scan-Rate	240 RPM
PRF	2880 RPM
Target Range	6 nm
Resolution	1 m
Azimuth Beamwidth	2 deg
N_p (pulsar per beam)	16
N_r (range cells)	256
Radar height	250 meters
Wind direction	Upwind
Look direction	Upwind
CNR	[30 -30 10 0]
SINR per pulse	[10 5 0 -10]
Sea State	3
T_s	2 seconds
T_r	11.5 meters
T_c	10
grazing angle	0.0173 deg
ν	0.16

TABLE III
BEAMLET TBD PARAMETERS

θ	$\pi/8$
ρ	4 meters
P	20
Λ	128
d	4 meters
Scales	[8 16 32 64]

TABLE IV
PERCENTAGE DETECTION FOR 100 SIMULATION RUNS CELL-AVERAGING
BASED CLUTTER

SINR (rows) CNR	30	0	-10	-30
10	100	100	100	100
5	95	100	100	100
0	0	4	54	100
-10	0	0	0	0

TABLE V
PERCENTAGE DETECTION FOR 100 SIMULATION RUNS CELL-AVERAGING
BASED CLUTTER FOR CNR OF 30 DECIBELS AND DIFFERENT SINRS

SINR (dB)	0	1	2	3	4	5
detection rate	0	3	22	49	74	95

Fig. 5. Beamlet TBD output at step 3 of the algorithm for an SNIR of zero and CNR of 30 dB

Fig. 6. Beamlet TBD output at step 3 of the algorithm for an SNIR of 5 dB and CNR of 30 dB

Fig. 7. Beamlet TBD output at step 3 of the algorithm for an SNIR of zero dB and CNR of -30 dB

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